

Preliminary Identification of Future Needs with respect to Heavy Liquid Metal Core and Pool Thermal Hydraulics

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Introduction

- Nuclear energy provides carbon free electricity and heat.
- Uranium reserves can serve the world for 1 or 2 centuries with a once-through cycle in LWRs.
- Liquid metal fast reactors increase sustainability of the fuel cycle providing energy for the coming millenia. Lead fast reactors (critical and subcritical) are under consideration in Europe.
- In the past decennia, a lot of R&D work was performed in Europe. This provides a starting point for definition of future activities.
- Core and pool thermal hydraulics are being considered and examples will be provided.

LFR and ADS

Introduction

- Two LFR designs (IAEA ARIS):

ALFRED

ALFRED	MYRRHA
Ansaldo - ENEA	SCK CEN
Demonstrator	Experimental
300 MWth / 125 MWe	100 MWth
Pb	PbBi
400-480°C	270-325°C
Fuel Assembly	Fuel Assembly
Grid-spaced	Wire-wrapped
127 pins	127 pins
D = 10.5 mm	D = 6.55 mm
p/D = 1.32	p/D = 1.28

MYRRHA

Introduction

Topic	Experiment	Simulation	Organisation(s)
Fuel Assembly	NACIE liquid metal 		
	AUPINEL water 		
	KALLA liquid metal 		
Pool	MYRRHAbelle water facility 		
	ESCAPE liquid metal facility 		

- Two collaborative European projects bring together experiments and simulations for fuel assembly and pool thermal hydraulics

- Preliminary conclusions from state-of-the-art assessments and identification of future needs.

Core Thermal Hydraulics

Assessing State-of-the-art and Future Needs

- Nominal geometries and conditions
 - Sufficient knowledge has been obtained. Simulations sufficiently accurate in view of safety margins.
 - Upper bounds accuracy peak cladding temperature known. Reduce bounds through better understanding of velocity profiles.
 - (partial) Wetting heat transfer mostly neglected and not understood.
 - Chemistry: numerical models under development but need of experimental confirmation.
 - Flow induced vibrations no challenge for MYRRHA. However, not conclusive for other designs.
- Deformations
 - Pin and/or wrapper deformations remain open question. Variety is too large to draw conclusions.
- Blockages
 - Blockage studies reveal mismatch between CFD and experimental results only partly understood.
 - Detection increased peak temperatures.
- Complete core
 - Complete core simulation (incl. inter-wrapper or bypass flow) is numerical challenge.
- Severe accidents
 - Severe accident fuel relocation and accumulation: possibly combination of DEM and CFD.

MYRRHA
fuel assembly
(SCK CEN)

Core Thermal Hydraulics

Deformations

- Grid spaced bundles
 - Water experiment
 - AUPINEL 7-pin bundle (VKI)
 - Center pin bended towards gap of neighbouring edge pins
 - PbBi experiment
 - NACIE 19-pin bundle (ENEA)
 - 3 pre-bended pins (corner, edge, internal)
 - Pre-test simulations for both experiments
 - Pre-test NACIE benchmark (CRS4, ENEA, VKI, NRG PALLAS) published by Dalvi et al., 2025 (NE&D 114293)

NACIE loop (ENEA)

Core Thermal Hydraulics

Deformations

- Wire-wrapped bundles
 - Water experiment
 - AUPINEL 7-pin bundle (VKI)
 - Deformed center pin
 - PbBi experiment
 - KALLA THESYS loop 7-pin bundle (KIT)
 - Deformed corner pin by piston
 - Mock-up experiment with epoxy-resin to determine shape
- Pre-test simulations for both experiments
 - THESYS: combination of thermo-mechanical and CFD simulations by Roelofs et al., 2023 (ANS WM)
- 'post'-test simulations of THESYS epoxy-resin mock-up

unpolished

polished

Pool Thermal Hydraulics

Assessing State-of-the-art and Future Needs

- Experiments and instrumentation
 - Improve liquid metal flow measurement techniques.
 - Characterization of the experimental facility (weight, surface finish, insulation, instrumentation type and positions, heat losses...) supporting simulation definition.
- Simulations
 - Additional validation data needed. Experiments or high-resolution numerical data.
 - Can theoretical mesh requirements be relaxed?
 - Modelling large components:
 - Pump and core model limitations understood.
 - Improvement and validation of CFD models for heat exchangers.
 - Modelling stratification and fatigue damage.
 - Development and validation turbulent heat transfer models applicable to all flow conditions.
 - Chemical interaction models incl. effect of impurities.
 - Sloshing.
 - Gas entrainment occurrence and impact.
 - Solidification.
 - Interaction with water.
- Severe accidents
 - Behavior of molten fuel in heavy liquid metal core and pool.

*Inner loop of the
CIRCE facility
(ENEA)*

Core Thermal Hydraulics Benchmarks

- MYRRHAbelle (Planquart & Van Tichelen, 2019)
 - MYRRHA design v1.2
 - 1:5 scale water mock-up
 - Limited heating (no boiling)
 - Instrumentation
 - Pressure taps
 - PIV
 - Thermocouples
 - Loss-of-Flow, Loss-of-Coolant, Single HEX failure
- New Benchmark
 - Single Pump Failure
 - Analogy to experiment in ESCAPE (next slide)

*MYRRHAbelle facility
(VKI)*

Core Thermal Hydraulics Benchmarks

- ESCAPE (Van Tichelen et al., 2015 & 2025)
 - MYRRHA design 1.2
 - 1:6 scale LBE mock-up
 - Electric core simulator (representative for decay heat power)
 - Instrumentation
 - ~300 thermocouples
 - Mass flow rate
 - Pressure drop
 - LBE level
 - Loss-of-Flow, partial Loss-of-Heat Sink, ...
- New Benchmark
 - Loss-of-Flow with partial Loss-of-Heat Sink Scenario
 - Combination of scenarios previously studied
 - Challenging for simulation codes

ESCAPE
(SCK CEN)

Conclusions & Outlook

Identified R&D gaps:

- Development of measurement techniques in liquid metal, specifically for local velocity.
- Fuel assembly deformations and blockages
- Complete core (incl. bypass flow) simulation methods
- Fuel debris relocation
- Effect of wetting on flow and heat transfer
- Chemistry effects on flow and heat transfer
- Fluid Structure Interaction in the core and pool
- Development of best practices to support students, young professionals and other newcomers to the field
- Creation of additional validation data, experiments and/or high-resolution simulations targeting specific purposes
- Sloshing
- Gas entrainment
- Solidification
- Interaction between heavy liquid metal and water
- Consequences of a fuel melt severe accident in the core and pool
- Uncertainty quantification

Additional suggestions?

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